

EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL INVESTIGATION OF DEBONDING BEHAVIOR OF EXTERNALLY REPAIRED LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: The Bonding strength was evaluated using Crack Lap Shear test based on energy release rate under fatigue loading. This test method is very simple and easy to measure crack length. However, this test method has disadvantage of displaced center since a test specimen is not symmetry. A new data reduction method was proposed considering tension and bending moment due to displaced axis. Energy release rate is a measure of the energy available for an increment of debonding growth. Total energy release rate in this test specimen can be distributed to between energy release rate due to tension and that due to bending moment. Goland-Reissner's results were used about bending moment, M_0 . In this test method, debonding growth was stable. Energy release rate was constant under constant loading because energy release rate is independent of debonding length. The applicability and the limitation of the proposed data reduction were examined using finite element solution. In fact, young's modulus and thickness of FRP laminates have an influence on the rate of energy release rates due to tension and that due to bending moment. Also, change of rate of energy release rates due to tension and that due to bending moment was evaluated due to debonding growth. Characterization of bonding strength between externally repaired FRP laminates and steel was evaluated under fatigue loading using cracked lap shear test. A relation between compliance and debonding length based on proposed data reduction conformed to experimental relation. Energy release rate due to bending moment was about 25% of total energy release rate. Relation between debonding growth and energy release rate under fatigue loading could be expressed in Paris-law.

KEYWORDS: Bonding strength, Externally repaired CFRP, Fracture toughness, Adhesive joint and Cracked Lap shear test

INTRODUCTION

As a large number of bridges and marine structures are increasingly being declared unsafe, economical ways must be found to restore such infrastructure to its original safe condition. Repair and retrofitting are much more economical than rebuilding. In addition, infrastructure is difficult to be rebuilt since its functions cannot be stopped in daily use. Repairing techniques with externally-bonded FRP sheets and structural adhesives are increasingly being adopted in concrete structures and aircraft because of high rigidity, lightweight and easy fabrication required for these applications. There is a considerable demand for developing new repair techniques that can rehabilitate steel structures rapidly and economically.

The authors have studied on the efficiency of repairing CFRP patch for cracked structures. The stress intensity factor at crack tip and energy release rate of debonding between the composite wrap and beam was derived in the normalized closed-form equations based on linear fracture mechanics [1]. The repairing efficiency CFRP patch on resistance of crack propagation of single-edge notched steel beam under static and fatigue loading was evaluated experimentally [2]. Under static loading, crack propagation of steel beam was not observed, on the other hand, under fatigue loading, both crack propagation of steel beam and debonding growth between repairing CFRP and steel beam occurred. High modulus CFRP had a higher efficiency on resistance of crack propagation than high strength CFRP. However, debonding growth of test specimen repaired with high modulus CFRP was faster. Efficiency of resistance of crack propagation depends on debonding length. From this reason, it is important to clarify behavior of debonding growth between repairing CFRP patch and damaged beam under fatigue loading.

In this paper, bonding strength was evaluated using a test method of Cracked Lap Shear (CLS) based on energy release rate under fatigue loading, as shown in Fig.1. This test method is very simple and easy to measure debonding length. However, this test method has disadvantage of displaced axis since a test specimen is not symmetric. A new data reduction method was proposed considering tension and bending moment due to displaced axis. The validity of the new data reduction method was examined and applied to evidence the relation between debonding length growth and energy release rate at interface between repaired FRP sheets and steel.

Fig. 1 Schematic image of cracked lap shear test

TESTING METHOD OF BONDING STRENGTH

Many test methods [3-5] have been proposed to evaluate bonding strength based on average bonding stress. A strength that critical ultimate load divided by bonding area is called average bonding stress. However, average bonding stress neglects the effect of stress concentration at tip of delamination. This parameter is not inherent of material. From this reason, it is important that bonding strength is evaluated based on fracture toughness. However, fracture toughness is difficult to evaluate because fracture toughness test is complicated [6-8] and because it is difficult to measure a crack length. The authors proposed new test method and data reduction for evaluation of bonding strength [9]. In this test method, bonding strength was evaluated based on fracture toughness without measurement of debonding length. However, fatigue test take a long time using this test method, because deflection depends on debonding length.

Lap shear test has been used for evaluation of bonding strength of adhesive. 3 types of lap shear test are used: single lap shear test, CLS test and double lap shear (DLS) test. Single lap shear test and double lap shear test have an advantage of symmetric test specimen. However, these test specimens have two crack paths. CLS test has the advantage of easy measurement of the debonding length because crack path is only one for single lap joint and because crack tip opens under tensile loading. However, neutral axis is displaced in this test specimen because this test specimen is not symmetric. CLS test was applied for measuring mixed-mode interlaminar fracture toughness [10].

1. CLS test method

Fig. 2 Schematic image of test method of CLS

Bonding strength was evaluated based on energy release rate used by CLS test. Figure 2 shows schematic of CLS test methods. Neutral axis is displaced in this test specimen because this test specimen is not symmetric. Bending moment is applied to this test specimen under tensile loading. A new data reduction method to evaluate bonding strength based on energy release rate was proposed considering bending moment.

2 Proposed data reduction method

Many investigator analyzed fracture toughness of CLS test specimen using a compliance method [11]. However, the result neglects bending moment in tension loading. A new data reduction method was proposed under consideration of bending moment.

Total energy release rate in this test specimen can be distributed to between energy release rate due to tension and that due to bending moment. Total energy release rate is expressed as

$$G_{Total} = G_{Tension} + G_{Moment} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3 Schematic image of debonding growth of CLS test

Figure 3 shows a schematic of debonding growth under tensile loading. On the right side in Fig.3, tensile load, P , is applied with only CFRP sheet. On the other hand, on the left side, tensile load, P , is applied with both CFRP sheet and steel. Young's modulus of CFRP and steel are E_{cf} and E_s . Thickness of CFRP and steel are t_{cf} and t_s . Propagated debonding length is Δc . Width of both CFRP and steel is B . Energy release rate was analyzed based on the energy available for an increment of debonding growth. Energy release rate due to tensile load is expressed as

$$G_{Tension} = -\frac{\Delta U}{Bdc} = \frac{P^2}{2B^2} \cdot \frac{1}{(E_{CF}t_{CF} + E_S t_s)} \cdot \frac{E_S t_s}{E_{CF}t_{CF}} \quad (2)$$

Alternatively, Energy release rate due to moment is expressed using equivalent flexural rigidity, \overline{EI} as

$$G_{Moment} = -\frac{M_0^2}{2B} \left(\frac{1}{\overline{EI}_{after}} - \frac{1}{\overline{EI}_{before}} \right) \quad (3)$$

where \overline{EI}_{before} is a equivalent flexural rigidity before debonding growth, \overline{EI}_{after} is a equivalent flexural rigidity after debonding growth. Goland-Reissner's expressions were used bending moment, M_0 .

Goland-Reissner analyzed bending moment in a lap joint [11]. The joint length is noted $2c$, the two joined sheets are considered to be of equal thickness t and are presumed to extended a distance l to either side of the joint. Tension load, P , was applied to the edges of each lap joint. The expression for M_0 was given as a function of the applied force P :

$$M_0 = \frac{1}{2} \kappa P t$$

$$\kappa = \frac{ch(\xi c)}{ch(\xi c) + 2\sqrt{2}sh(\xi c)}, \quad \xi = \sqrt{\frac{3P}{2EI}} \quad (4)$$

Here κ accounted for bending moment reduction. In this test, κ was 0.28, a constant, because joint length, c , was very long.

FEM ANALYSIS

In this study, a finite element code, COSMOS/M, was used with quadrilateral four nodes elements in order to check the applicability of the proposed data reduction. The model, as shown in Fig. 4, was analyzed under plane strain condition. Four types of thickness of CFRP and two types of CFRP were repaired. In addition to, twenty one types of initial debonding length were modeled: from 0 to 100mm at 5mm intervals. Energy release rate was numerically evaluated based on relation between load-deflection compliance and crack length.

Relation between this slope, $d\lambda/dc$ and energy release rate is expressed as:

Fig. 4 Schematic image of FEM model

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2B} \cdot \frac{d\lambda}{dc} \quad (5)$$

Relation between load-deflection compliance and crack length of all the models was shown in Fig. 5.

The slope, $d\lambda/dc$, was evaluated from 40mm to 100mm in crack length, because relation between compliance and crack length was linear, except $t=1\text{mm}$. Relation between thickness and $d\lambda/dc$ is shown in Fig. 6. It was shown that proposed data reduction agreed well with FEM for the thicker CFRP. From this result, the thickness of CFRP was chosen as 2.5mm

EXPERIMENT

1. Test specimen and test method

In this experiment, SS410, which is widely used in ship construction in Japan, was used as reinforcing steel. The composite used in this experiment was made of high modulus carbon sheet, which was FTS-C8-30 of Nippon steel composite. The fibers were in tow-sheet form, which was basically a layer of dry unidirectional fiber attached to a glass scrim. This material was widely used to reinforce RC structure in Japan. Material properties of this carbon fiber were shown in Table 1.

The width of the specimen was 25 mm, the height was about 4 mm, and the length was 250 mm. The thickness of steel was 2mm and 3ply high modulus carbon was laid on steel to give the thickness of 2.5mm. The length of lap joint was 130mm with an initial debonding length of 10mm, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 7. 30mm from the both end of specimen were chucked. 3ply high modulus carbon was made by hand-lay-up method on steel with initial debonding length using Teflon film.

Table 1 Material properties of Tow-Sheet

Item	FTS-C8-30
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Fiber	High modulus carbon
Weight per area / kg/m ²	0.3
Thickness / mm	0.143
Tensile strength per width / N/mm	2.7x10 ⁵
Tensile strength / N/m ²	1.9x10 ⁹
Extension rigidity / N/m	9.15x10 ⁷
Young's modulus / N/m ²	6.4x10 ¹¹
Elongation / %	0.3

Fig. 7 Size of CLS test specimen

The procedure for manufacturing this specimen was as follows: first step is sanding steel with grinder. Second step is removing grease with acetone. Third step is attaching the suitable sized Tow sheet by hand-lay-up method. Fourth step is curing for one week.

This test specimen was loaded under constant fatigue load. Four kinds of maximum load were used: 12.2kN, 9.8kN, 7.9kN and 4.9kN. A stress ratio of R is 0.1. The test frequency is about 8Hz. Load and displacement signal were obtained using a PC with data acquisition system. Debonding length was measured using a microscope.

2. Result

Relation between debonding length and compliance is shown in Fig. 8. From this figure, the compliance was not increased below 40mm of debonding length. From this reason, debonding tip is not sharp to manufacture initial debonding length using cutter. However the compliance was increased linearly above 40mm of debonding length. A linear line can be drawn for relation between debonding length and compliance above 40mm. A slope of the line was 1.16×10^{-6} .

Fig. 8 Relation between debonding length and compliance in CLS test

Alternatively, the slope, dl/dc , was analyzed based on proposed data reduction method. The theoretical slope was 1.14×10^{-6} . Theoretical relation between compliance and debonding length conform with experimental relation. The theoretical slope can be distributed to that due to tension and that due to bending moment. In this test specimen, energy release rate due to bending moment accounted for 25% of total energy release rate.

Relations between fatigue cycle and Δ debonding length were shown in Fig. 9.

In test specimen that maximum load was 4.9kN, CFRP sheet was broken before debonding growth was observed. Relation between debonding length growth and compliance became stabilized over 10mm of Δ debonding length. However, in test specimen that maximum load was 7.9kN, debonding was propagated in interlaminar over 50mm of Δ debonding length. For this reason, debonding growth rate was measured from 10mm to 50mm of Δ debonding length.

The relation between Δ energy release rate and debonding growth rate was shown in Fig. 10.

Open circles in Fig.10 were average of debonding growth rate. Relation between fatigue debonding growth rate and Δ energy release rate was applied to Paris law. Paris law was expressed as:

$$\frac{dc}{dN} = C_c (\Delta G)^{m_c} \quad (6)$$

Linear line could be drawn for relation between debonding growth rate and Δ energy release rate range. m_c and C_c in material constant were represented as a follow.

$$\begin{aligned} m_c &= 2.7 \\ C_c &= 0.12 \end{aligned} \quad (7) \quad \begin{matrix} Fi \\ cy \end{matrix}$$

Fig. 10 Relation between debonding growth rate and ΔG

CONCLUSION

Characterization of bonding strength between externally bonded FRP sheet and steel was evaluated under fatigue loading using cracked lap shear test. New data reduction method considering bending moment due to eccentric neutral axis was proposed to evaluate bonding strength based on fracture mechanics. In this test method, debonding growth was stable. Energy release rate was constant under constant loading because energy release rate is independent of debonding length. Energy release rate was evaluated using FEM models based on relation between compliance and crack length. As a result, the thicker CFRP became, the better relation the dl/dc based on FEM and proposed data reduction have. Theoretical relation between compliance and debonding length conformed with experimental relation. Energy release rate due to bending moment was about 25% of total energy release rate. Relation between debonding growth and energy release rate under fatigue loading could be expressed in Paris-law.

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